

THE PSYCHIC ENERGY

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Abstract: Jung, as a good psychiatrist, is also a philosopher. In your text, *The Psychic energy* 1928, Jung presents a very curious view because he claims that our psyche is a “concentration of energy”. In addition to being a philosopher, he could be considered an “occultist”, as it is demonstrated in the text how psychic energy *transform* into physical energy. Therefore, this brief essay presents my view on this text. Our method is phenomenological. And our goal is to clarify this vision a little.

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Introduction

Carl Gustav Jung (1875-1961) wrote an analytical psychology text known as “The Psychic Energy (1928)”. When encountering this text of yours, the aforementioned title caught my attention on a simple point, namely, Jung, as an orthodox psychiatrist, coming from the Freudian School, characterizes, in this particular text, the “psyche” as a “reservoir of accumulation of energy.” Now, it was precisely this word “energy” that led me to immediately read your text. In this sense, the essay presented here tries to get closer to what Jung wrote at the moment in which it reveals my perception and/or vision on the subject. So, this essay, more than a contribution, is a tribute that I pay to Jung for bringing this innovative and contemporary text to the field of psychology. Therefore, as I said, my vision will be presented on what “psychic energy” actually is, what its consequences are and what I, as the author of this essay, could “add” new about Jung’s vision. Finally, our method is phenomenological.

The similarity between “physical energy” and “psychic energy”

At a certain point in the text “Psychic Energy”, Jung ([1928] (2002)) says - “transformation is the expression of life”. Regarding the vital energy of psychic life, this statement fits perfectly

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with the meaning that “energy is the transformation and expression of life itself”. In other words, if we elevate this thought of ours to a very inner and deep level, we can extract only “energy” from it. Well, “everything is energy!” All life *external* or *internal* It is, once again, “energy”. In other words, in the extraction and dissection of the universe, what will result perfectly and with absolute accuracy is “energy”. *Everything above and everything below is an absolute composite of energy.* In this sense, the perception of energy or the process of energizing something itself is the *feedback* of the relationship between energies which, in the best known case, is defined by the “union of opposites”. In physics, for example, the best known “energy flow” is the positive relationships on one side and negative relationships on the other of the atoms. Thus, in the set of electrons that the atom makes up, the “breath of a ‘psychic’ way of life survives”. For, as Alice Bailey (2007) once said - “every atom or every atomic relation has ‘consciousness’”. Therefore, the abstract existence of this “psychic” atomic abstraction is due to the fact that the atom, in itself, is a *quite* transmitter and/or propagator of “energy”. We can say like this - “the raw material of energy is the *relations* as well as the raw material of relationships is the *energy*. With this, each or all nature of things, including material and immaterial ones, are entirely composed of “energy relations”. If the scientist looks closely, every abstraction of a phenomenon (physical or psychic) leads to an energetic way of seeing, that is, the entire *consonance* and/or *dissonance* in the universe of things it takes place in an “energetic vision”. Now, if everything is energy, the nature of everything is also energy. In an almost absolutely “material” world like ours, “physical nature” or “physical phenomenon” is a transparent and clear example of how energy starts to “flow” in every pore of matter. Thus, matter or all matters are, par excellence, “energy”, but a type of “condensed” and/or “coagulated” energy because, without the stimulus of atoms as well as ethers (and other “substances”) , the transformation of that “matter” into “living material energy” could not be possible. Therefore, the concept of “atom consciousness” fits perfectly here.

In this sense, “physical energy” is not only similar to “psychic energy”, but, both, are the reflection of each. What do we mean by this? We can respond in three points along with Von Grot cited by Jung ([1928] (2002)), “1. Psychic energies are ‘quantities’ and ‘magnitudes’, like those of a physical nature; 2. They are reciprocal in themselves; 3. They can be converted into physical energy and vice versa (through physiological processes)”. In other words, in the physiology of a psychic phenomenon, the flow of energy necessarily occurs due to the organic part of its relationship in the physical environment. Neither the physical nor the psychic would be able to “survive” without their inherent reciprocity. *The physical needs the psychic and the psychic needs the physical.* If we are to extract the entire flow of energy from a given “psychic organism”, what will result is a balance of forces between the *physical part* and others *psychic part*. What could say that there is, energetically speaking, a concentration of a quantity of value as much *physical* as *psychic*. As for example in the

concentrating force of a *core* of an atom that corresponds to its intensity, that is, to the accumulation of energy condensation. Because, energy is also “value” as every concentration and/or accentuation of affections appears as an “affective tone” precisely because of the extraordinary and immeasurable concentration of “affective energy”. Thus, the burden of emotions physically and psychically is a *quantum* of condensed, different and yet “balanced” energy. We can see this when a thought penetrates and permeates space, without even needing to be “incorporated” by the word and/or sound mass. I addressed this in a recent article of mine².

Jung, in this text, speaks of “quality” and “quantity” *psychic*. That is, the *which* and the *quantum*. Psychic energy is a “force”, nothing more than that. And, as a “force”, it has all the possible attributes of nature to transform things both prospectively and retroactively. Not energization, but “energy” itself is, on the whole, a “force”. When we talk about “energies” in the plural, it can also be interpreted as “forces” in the plural. These “forces” are both *qualia* How much *quantum*. An example: the strength and/or temporal energy of the present (of the present moment) happens due to the relationship *retrospective* (past) and *prospective* (future). Because the present as an absolute present is nothing more than a *momentum* that cannot “move”. However, the transparency or clarity of this even psychic phenomenon is not physically present because temporality is, in its entirety, an “abstraction”, in this case, “reflective”. The phenomenon of “psychic abstraction” itself is already a “physical phenomenon” in advance because it is already psychic and vice versa. And we say more, the “psychic phenomenon” itself is like this because of the accumulation of concentrated energy within the psyche, joining part of the fundamental physical energy to this. That is why, since around the 19th century, people have spoken of “psychic mass” to clarify the psychic phenomenon and its meaning a little better. *abstraction* through the mind and the physical environment.

Like the mass of an atom + energy, the psyche is also like this, that is, the physiological and organic part is similar not only because “energy” is conserved and distributed, but because there is also equality and inequality of atoms in the psyche. Only the *qualia* (or “quality”) in the psyche is very different from the quality in the physical part. Thus, even if the “effects” on the physical and psychic levels are not of equal order and quality, the *virtual process* of transformation into living and current energy is *equal*. The psychic quality of a psychic mass as a *thought* it has *quantities* and *magnitudes* similar to the physical qualities of all matter. In a cosmological view, the Creator, in His Perfect act, created not only the “physical” part of the universe, but, in this same first actualizing act, also gave birth, at the same time of the act, to the “psychic” part of the universe, or that is, the *virtual or reflex image* of His first act. And then “universe” means “the set or sum of all things”. Unfortunately, materialistic science is still too far away to recognize the “conscious” and/or

² SANTOS, C. *How does thought penetrate and permeate space?* Zenodo, 1-9, 2024.

psychic” part in every phenomenon that is not “living” or “purely material”. In other words, the vision of the *pampsychism*. This “vision” believes that everything, exactly everything, has, within its interiority, a “vital energy”, even in merely “visible” and/or “material” things. It turns out that the meaning of “vital”, which means “vitality”, already has a “psychic” part in it. A thing can only “possess” a “vital energy” if it is, above all, “conscious”. And, in Jungian saying, *all physical life is, at its substrate, a psychic life*. Thus, the immanence of clarity or the “clarity immanent in things” can only be *reflection* of a “conscious” state and/or organism functioning there.

Regarding psychic mass, we are in agreement with Jung ([1928] (2002)) in this text, when he says - “Energy is nothing more than the *expression* or the *signal* of a *energy system*”. Therefore, this means that the accumulation of psychic energy somewhere in the mind appears to us as a “complex energetic system”. Thus, the “psyche” is nothing more than a *system*, above all, also “physiological” because all this “accumulation” of vital and psychic energy could only flow through a “physiological” system which is, in this case, “the concrete part of the mind”. However, for Jung, “the psyche is a relatively closed system”. Let's see, Jung, in addition to calling the psyche a “system”, characterizes it as “closed”. This statement is very difficult because if the human or animal psyche is a “relatively closed system”, would the “cerebral organism” be the thing that “closes” the psyche? Not the mind, but the brain? Even today, neurosciences still ask a lot about how psychic currents or the flow of thought manage to “overcome” this “relatively closed field and/or system” and make the living being *realize* and *feel* all the psychic quality of its mode of appearance to the mind? In other words, like the psyche *reflects* a certain psychic quality? And more, how do you externalize it? Jung says “relatively closed system”, that is, “relatively” and not “totally”; What this demonstrates is that the psyche is a “relatively open field or system as well” because, through some physiological mechanism, a psychic quality *in transit* the material and/or physical environment (your closed psychic energetic system) and *raisin* to the external environment.

And then, in this text, Jung ([1928] (2002)) speaks of “entropy” in physics to demonstrate that something similar occurs in the psyche. He says - “Entropy means: the stronger the tension between opposites, the greater the resulting amount of energy.” It is like this in the atom, so in every psychic quality it will be as well. For Jung, “psychic energy” means “the expression of psychological value relationships”. In other words, in a “regression”, the more the individual regresses the psychic mass of thought, the more the “conscious” side causes the opposite movement. It would be the “unconscious” and the “conscious”. It is still said today that the “unconscious” would still be an “entity”; which demonstrates that he is a “living being” always in action because, in the pure virtuality that he is, he “actualizes” himself in the physiological processes of the psyche that are inherent to them. This phenomenon is similar to when we throw a

bowling ball (iron) with a certain force to knock down the elements in front. The more we put, the more tension, which means “actuated and acting force”, that is, the more “energy”, the more “force”. The same happens with “psychic force”. When we want to remember an event at a given moment, we insert and/or exert a good portion of psychic energy until the memory, like a flash, reawakens from its “deep sleep”. Thus, all the depths of the psyche, if we are to recover, we will have to attribute a “centripetal force” in order to “excavate” in the unconscious part our traits and/or psychological values that relate to our “self”.

At another point in the text, Jung ([1928] (2002)) states - “Energy is only accessible to experience precisely through direct observation of the behavior of *moving substances*”. In other words, the “I” only perceives the “movement” of a thought when this thought, as a psychic mass, “moves”. So, in a concrete way, direct observation of the phenomenon in action becomes necessary so that it also “exists” within the mind. This is why, according to Jung, “the psychological concept of ‘energy’ is not pure, but concrete and applied”. Therefore, in our view, Jung means that what really makes a phenomenon or psychological value “concrete” is the observance of the experience of the “psychic experience” itself. The Latin *virtue* means “force”, therefore, everything that is, by nature, “virtual”, has origin and is properly a “force”. Why? Simply because every psychic act would not be an “act” without the mirror of its act, which is the “virtual act”. This is the same act only in its own way *reverse*.

More than an exteriority, psychic energy is an “intensity” because what is subtracted from all psychological value is the clear intensity of conservation of psychic energy. For this, Jung ([1928] (2002)) in the text uses a simple example - “The intensity of progression appears again in the intensity of regression”. It would be like physically the positive pole and the negative pole of the atom; they repel each other and, in this repulsion, they produce “drive” again. Every action has a reaction and in every drive there is a repulsion. Thus, the same “force” happens in the psyche. When the individual attributes a certain force to remembering the past, this same “force” appears again pointing back to the present. This “unknown force” that, at the same time as it connects two different moments, in the same propulsion, returns to the primary state; in Jung's view, it could only be “energy” and, in this case, “psychic”. Still in Jung's view, this would be a “transfer of intensities or psychic values from one content to another”. So, for example, when we have the pleasure and/or libido of “smoking cigarettes” and in return “we go for a pleasant run”. It turns out that the urge to “smoke” that was appeased with “running” returns once again, without ceasing, to its even more “deep” or “raw” state; which results in saying that “the lack of tension in a thing also results in the appearance of that”. In the words of Jung ([1928] (2002)), this would be “a transference to the *analogue* of the original object.”

Thus, “psychic energy” would not only be the “reflection” of the “physical” image of the universe and the things that make it up, but much more its *psychic imago*, that is, the *reflex image* of the entire perceptual act. Because, when the psyche “perceives”, the image of perception and/or act is already contained there when the “act and/or psychological value” is nothing more than a *virtual act*. In this order, the “psyche” is almost absolutely composed of “virtual constituents” when the mind, all of it, reflects, in the most perfect way possible, all of reality; not only its contour, but its entire phenomenal constitution of appearance. If there is something “material” in the psyche of the psyche, this must be due to the intrinsic relationship of the mind with reality, in this case, above all “physics”. What happens is that if in every physical phenomenon a “physiology” is used, this necessarily demonstrates that, at the level of expression of psychological values, the psyche also has, in its ontogenesis, a part that is declared “physical” and/or “material”. Because, otherwise, how could this same psychological value be “distributed” or even “conserved” within the mind without a “concrete” support? Thus, the view that the universe is, in its constitution, double becomes even clearer; is a *duplex image*, preserving its own “structure” and the “structure of *imago* of the mind.” Because, in this domain, one thing must be clear: the universe is also a “universal mind” that also preserves everything that “receives” and/or is “transmitted” from the “operating minds of man, as well as animal beings”. Well, again, *everything is energy*. And, energy is everything! Because, as Jung ([1928] (2002)) states, “everything that acts from the unconscious appears projected onto others”. Which means that everything else or accumulation of energy conserved in a physical or psychic environment ends up, to some extent and in some way, being *released* or *designed* in the psyche of others. Then, *We are the being of today because we were the being of before*. In other words, the very complex question of “heredity” or “past lives”. That, in the words of Jung ([1928] (2002)), “the heredity of the ‘previous’ or invisible parents is the sum of the records that is born again in the child”. What Jung himself called this phenomenon *the collective consciousness*. Regarding psychic energy, this is true because, even in occult terms, all the pain and suffering of the present age is due to *substantially* to the remains of pain and suffering from all past lives. Thus, all the rest of the dark and destructive psychic energy built up in previous ages (reflected in the psyches of others) probably triggered the *image* of our world in the 21st century, namely, a “dark and chaotic earthly world”. Perhaps, the *inverse forces* They are the ones who have dominated the world.

Conclusion

As a conclusion to this brief essay, we can say more or less the following - with regard to “psychic energy”, it is a great spiritual force that *creates* the world and all life in it. It turns out that, even “psychically”, we are creating not only our reality, but that of all life. Furthermore, the concept of “collective consciousness” serves us a lot and is true when we are only made up of a “physical” part, because the “psychic” part “commands” it. So, when it comes to the modern world, why is it that a large majority of people are undergoing psychoanalysis, psychology or psychiatrist sessions? Perhaps this essay of ours explained a little of this.

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